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● Taxonomic revision of the genus *Callimerus* Gorham s. l. (Coleoptera, Cleridae). Part II. *prasinatus* species group

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Abstract: This study revises the *prasinatus* species group of the genus *Callimerus* (Coleoptera, Cleridae), *sensu* *Stenocallimerus* Corporaal & Pic, 1940. Ten species are recognized, including one new species, *Callimerus modestus* sp. nov., from northeastern Vietnam. Two new synonyms are proposed for *C. koenigi* Pic, 1954 (*C. koenigi* var. *subattenuatus* Pic, 1954 **syn. nov.**; *C. taiwanus* Miyatake, 1965 **syn. nov.**), and two for *C. prasinatus* Lewis, 1896 (*C. bicoloripes* Pic, 1925 **syn. nov.**; *C. sauteri* Corporaal & Pic, 1940 **syn. nov.**). *Callimerus filiformis* Gorham, 1903 is excluded from this species group. An identification key is presented, accompanied by illustrations of the type specimens' habitus, male terminalia, and other diagnostic characters. This revision refines the taxonomy of *prasinatus* species group and offers a foundation for future research on the group.

Keywords: *Callimerus*, checkered beetles, identification key, new species, *prasinatus* group, synonymy, taxonomy

● 丽郭公虫属 *Callimerus* Gorham s. l. 的分类学修订（鞘翅目：郭公虫科）第二部分——*prasinatus* 种团

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摘要：本研究对丽郭公虫属（鞘翅目：郭公虫科）中的 *prasinatus* 种团进行了分类修订。该种团共包含10个物种，其中包括1个新种——*Callimerus modestus* sp. nov.（分布于越南东北部）。提出四个新异名：*C. koenigi* var. *subattenuatus* Pic, 1954 和 *C. taiwanus* Miyatake, 1965 为 *C. koenigi* Pic, 1954 的次异名；*C. bicoloripes* Pic, 1925 和 *C. sauteri* Corporaal & Pic, 1940 为 *C. prasinatus* Lewis, 1896 的次异名。*Callimerus filiformis* Gorham, 1903 排出此种团。本文提供了 *prasinatus* 种团的分种检索表、模式标本的外部形态和雄性外生殖器结构图。本修订工作进一步完善了 *prasinatus* 种团的分类体系，为后续相关研究提供了基础。

关键词：丽郭公虫属，郭公虫，检索表，新种，*prasinatus* 种团，异名，分类

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● Introduction

This study represents the second revision of the genus *Callimerus* Gorham, 1876 (see Yang *et al.* 2013), with a focus on the *prasinatus* species group. This species group was previously treated as a separate genus, *Stenocallimerus* Corporaal & Pic, 1940. However, Kolibáč (1998) synonymized *Stenocallimerus* with *Callimerus*, noting that its only distinguishing feature was an elongated body shape and that it lacked diagnostic apomorphies to justify separation. On the other hand, Bartlett (2021) recently transferred *Callimerus* to the subfamily Clerinae.

In his catalogue, Corporaal (1950) listed nine valid species and one variety within *Stenocallimerus*. Four additional species and one variety were later described (Pic 1954; Miyatake 1965; Yajima & Nakane 1969), and the variety recorded by Corporaal (1950) was elevated to species rank by Nakane (1996). Most recently, Murakami (2025) synonymized *C. okinawanus* Yajima & Nakane, 1969 with *C. prasinatus* Lewis, 1896, a conclusion that matches the present author's assessment during preparation of this work. Consequently, prior to the present revision, *prasinatus* species group comprised 13 valid species and one variety.

The present study provides a taxonomic revision of the *prasinatus* species group of *Callimerus*. All species of this group are distributed in eastern Asia, and ten species are recognized in total. *Callimerus filiformis* Gorham, 1903 is excluded from the group because it lacks a basal claw tooth. One new species, *C. modestus* **sp. nov.** is described from northeastern Vietnam, and four new synonyms are proposed. An identification key to all recognized species is provided, along with illustrations of type specimens, male terminalia, and other diagnostic characters. A broader revision of the entire genus *Callimerus* will be presented in a subsequent study.

● Material and methods

Dissection methods and the terminology follow Yang *et al.* (2013). Terminological abbreviations used in the text are: EyD: minimum distance between two eyes; EyW: maximum eye width in dorsal view (Fig. 71); PL: prothorax maximum length; PW: prothorax maximum width; EL: elytra maximum length; EW: elytra maximum width; hw.: handwriting. Materials examined in this study are deposited in the following collections:

- CAU China Agricultural University, Beijing, China
- CBWX Collection of Mr. BI Wenxuan, Shanghai, China
- CCCC Collection of Mr. CHEN Changchin, Taiwan, China
- CXG Collection of Xavier Gouverneur, France
- CYGY Collection of Yang Ganyan, Beijing, China
- GZU Guizhou University, Guiyang, Guizhou, China
- IZAS Institute of Zoology, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing, China
- MNHN Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France
- NHMB Naturhistorisches Museum, Basel, Switzerland
- NHML The Natural History Museum, London, United Kingdom
- NHRS Naturhistoriska Riksmuseet, Stockholm, Sweden
- SNUC Insect Collection of Shanghai Normal University, Shanghai, China
- ZMAN Zoölogisch Museum Amsterdam, Leiden, The Netherlands

● Taxonomy

prasinatus species group

Stenocallimerus Corporaal & Pic, 1940: 189 (subgenus of *Callimerus* Gorham; type species: *Callimerus prasinatus* Lewis, 1896, by original designation); Corporaal 1950: 83 (Catalogue; raised to genus rank); Kolibáč 1998: 176 (synonymized with *Callimerus* Gorham);

prasinatus-group Kolibáč, 1998: 182.

Diagnosis. Body slenderer than in most *Callimerus* species (EL/EW 3.3–3.8 except for *C. bicoloritarsis* 2.7–2.8), integument metallic green, blue, or piceous; elytra usually with white scales forming patterns (Figs 1, 3, 5, 8, 18A) or just scattering over surface (Figs 11, 15, 18B); elytral apex round or sometimes outer angle visible (but not pointed); claw with a basal tooth (Yang *et al.* 2013: Fig. 57); metatibia with or without subapical projection on the outer edge. This species group differs from *coomani* species group (*sensu* Kolibáč, 1998) by claw with a basal tooth; from *dulcis* species group (*sensu* Kolibáč, 1998) by body slenderer, scales on the body surface more elongated, elytral apex not truncated; from *latifrons* species group by body slenderer, integument metallic green, blue, or piceous, EyD larger than EyW (ratio 1.4–2.6), elytra usually with scales, outer angle of elytral apex not pointed.

Description. *Size:* length 6.5–12.5 mm. *Integument color:* metallic green, blue, or piceous. *Vestiture:* body profusely vested with long, pale yellow or white pubescence (Fig. 18, see hollow arrow); frons, thoracic pleuron and lateral abdomen with dense, lanceolate white scales; elytra with white scales forming patterns, scattered irregularly over whole elytron surface or concentrated along sutural region without forming patterns, or entirely lacking scales. *Head:* including eyes slightly wider than pronotum, vertex with sparse punctures; labrum rectangular, apex straight or very slightly emarginate; mandibles stout; terminal segments of maxillary palpi digitiform, twice the length of penultimate segments; terminal segments of labial palpi elongate-triangular, as long as penultimate segments. Eyes large, finely granulate, slightly notched near antennal insertions; inner margin of eyes almost parallel, faintly convergent posteriorly, minimum interocular distance wider than maximum eye width in dorsal view (EyD/EyW 1.4–2.6). Antennae short, slightly longer than width of head; antennomere I stout and bent; antennomere II globular, slightly shorter than antennomere I; antennomere III longer than its width and longer than length of antennomere II; antennomeres IV–VIII increasingly widened and shorter than their preceding segments, antennomeres IX–XI forming a more or less compact and oval club, apex of antennomeres XI pointed. Gula oblong, gular sutures parallel. *Prothorax:* usually longer than wide, PL/PW ca. 1.4–1.5, only in one species (*C. bicoloritarsis*) PL/PW ca. 1.0; pronotum constricted at base, slightly dilated before middle; subapical impression of pronotum present; punctures on pronotum coarser and denser than those on vertex. *Elytra:* slightly wider than head including eyes, EL/EW 2.8–3.8; elytral lateral sides parallel, apex round or sometimes outer angles slightly distinct (but not pointed); punctures dense and coarse, not in rows; apart from the long pubescence, elytral surface with slender white scales arranged in distinct pattern (Figs 1, 3, 5, 8, 18A), or scattered randomly over elytra (Figs 11, 15A, 18B), or near suture (Figs 15C, E), or without scales. When forming definite pattern, with five spots on each elytron in ground plan (Fig. 3D): a subbasal spot situated approximately in basal 1/5 of elytron near suture, a median spot situated in middle near suture, an apical spot situated at apex; a lateral spot situated near margin between subbasal spot and median spot; and a subapical spot or transverse fascia situated between median spot and apical spot near margin. *Legs:* tibiae without longitudinal ridge; metatibia with or without a subapical projection on outer edge; tarsi formula 5-5-5, tarsomeres I–II slender, almost of equal length, both widened and slightly bilobed towards apex, possessing narrow but well visible pulvilli underneath; tarsomeres III–IV shorter than tarsomeres I and II, triangular and distinctly bilobed at apex, possessing broad pulvilli underneath; tarsomere V slender, without pulvillus; claw with a basal tooth (Yang *et al.* 2013, Fig. 57). *Abdomen:* with six ventrites; male sternite VIII normally emarginate at apex; female sternite VIII slightly elevated basally, with an apical flat area that, in some species, separates the basal elevation into two protuberances, female sternite VIII apex round, pointed or straight. *Male terminalia:* tegmen tubular, sclerotized, usually with three semi-transparent membranous regions: a pair of fissure-like areas on

dorsolateral surface (Fig. 6B), and one on ventral surface, somewhat cordiform-broad (Figs 6C, 10C), very small (Figs 9C, 12C), or absent in *C. micans*; in *C. tenuissimus*, an additional membranous region presents on dorsal surface (Figs 2A, B). Parameres strongly sclerotized, apices divergent or convergent, in some of the species hooked or with a denticle at apex. Phallic plate sclerotized in midline. Spicular fork: ratio of length of spicular apodeme to length of whole spicular fork 0.25–0.50.

Distribution. Only known from Eastern Asia (Figs 19, 20).

Species list. Ten species are included.

Callimerus tenuissimus Corporaal, 1926 (India)

Callimerus nigripes Corporaal, 1926

Callimerus angustior Pic, 1927 (Vietnam, China, Laos)

Callimerus maderi Corporaal, 1939 (China)

Callimerus micans Corporaal, 1940 (Myanmar, China)

Callimerus angustatus Pic, 1939 (Vietnam, China)

Callimerus apicalis Pic, 1954 (China)

Callimerus koenigi Pic, 1954 (China, Japan)

Callimerus subattenuatus Pic, 1954 **syn. nov.**

Callimerus taiwanus Miyatake, 1965 **syn. nov.**

Callimerus prasinatus Lewis, 1896 (China, Japan)

Callimerus bicoloripes Pic, 1925 **syn. nov.**

Callimerus sauteri Corporaal & Pic, 1940 **syn. nov.**

Callimerus okinawanus Yajima & Nakane, 1969

Callimerus bicoloritarsis Pic, 1925 (China)

Callimerus modestus **sp. nov.** (Vietnam)

Key to species of *prasinatus* species group

- 1 Elytron with white scales forming three to six spots, vittae, or fasciae (Figs 1, 3, 5, 18A).....2
- Elytron with scales restricted to a single apical spot (Fig. 8), scattered irregularly over whole elytron surface or concentrated along sutural region without forming patterns (Figs 11, 15, 18B), or entirely lacking scales (Fig. 13).....5
- 2 Each elytron with five or more spots of white scales (Fig. 3 A–D).....3
- Each elytron with three patches of white scales (Figs 5, 8).....4
- 3 Each elytron with a short vitta behind scutellum; five spots present, but lateral spot shifted anteriorly adjacent to subbasal spot, and subapical spot modified into a transverse fascia (Fig. 1); apices of parameres neither hooked nor denticulate (Figs 1, 2A, B).....*C. tenuissimus*
- Elytron without vitta behind scutellum, five spots as shown in Fig. 3.....*C. angustior*
- 4 Each elytron with a subbasal spot at basal fifth near suture, a round spot at apical third and another at apex; male abdominal tergite VIII straight or faintly emarginate apically, dorsal sinus of tegmen 3.5 times the length of paramere; widely distributed in eastern and southern China, alt. 500–1200 m (Figs 5A, 6).....*C. maderi*
- Each elytron with a short median vitta near suture, a narrow transverse fascia at apical fourth and a round apical spot; male abdominal tergite VIII rounded apically, dorsal sinus of tegmen twice the length of paramere; occurring at Kambaiti and adjacent Yunnan (Houqiao, Lushui) along the Myanmar–China boundary, alt. 1560–2580 m (Figs 5D, 7).....*C. micans*

- 5 Elytron with an apical spot of white scales (Fig. 8).....6
 - Elytron with scales scattered irregularly over whole elytron surface or along sutural region without forming patterns (Figs 11, 15, 18B), or lacking scales (Fig. 13).....7
 6 Metafemoral inner surface entirely yellow; male abdominal sternite VIII with prolonged lateral lobes (as long as sternite VIII along midline); dorsal sinus of tegmen slightly longer than ventral sinus; membranous region on ventral surface of tegmen very small, distinctly shorter than paramere (Figs 8A, 9).....*C. angustatus*
 - Apical half of metafemoral inner surface black; male abdominal sternite VIII simply emarginate apically, without prolonged lateral lobes; dorsal sinus deep, extending almost to internal limit of phallobase and twice the length of ventral sinus; membranous region on ventral surface of tegmen large, equal to paramere length (Figs 8D, 10).....*C. apicalis*
 7 Body robust; pronotum length subequal to width; EL/EW ≤ 2.8 (Figs 15A, 16).....*C. bicoloritarsis*
 - Body slender; pronotum distinctly longer than wide; EL/EW > 3.38
 8 Elytra with scales scattered over entire surface; male abdominal terminal segments highly specialized: tergite VIII swollen into two hemispheres with bluntly pointed apices; sternite VIII sclerotized, apically bifurcate, and tightly joined to tergite VIII; sternite VII apically bifurcate.....*C. koenigi*
 - Elytra without scales, or with very few scales restricted near suture; male abdominal terminal segments not specialized as above.....9
 9 Prolegs entirely yellow; male abdominal tergite VIII broadly and triangularly emarginate apically, sternite VIII with a pair of short apical projections; apices of parameres tapering, without denticle (Figs 13, 14); distributed in Japan to Taiwan.....*C. prasinatus*
 - Prolegs with outer edge of femora and tibiae black; male abdominal tergite VIII slightly rounded apically, sternite VIII broadly emarginate apically; each paramere apex with a denticle on outer margin (Figs 15C, 17); distributed in northern Vietnam.....*C. modestus* **sp. nov.**

Callimerus tenuissimus Corporaal, 1926

Figs 1, 2, 19

tenuissimus Corporaal, 1926: 176 (*Callimerus*; type locality: “Gopaldhara, Sikkim”).

nigripes Corporaal, 1926: 177 (*Callimerus tenuissimus* var.; type locality: “Gopaldhara, Sikkim”); Corporaal 1939: 193 (female of *C. tenuissimus* Corporaal); Löbl *et al.* 2007: 371 (synonym of *C. prasinatus*).

Type material examined. **Holotype** of *C. tenuissimus*. “Type / Gopaldhara, Nepal-Sikkim Frontier, H. Stevens, 1919 / H. Stevens. Brit. Mus. 1922-307 / J.B. Corporaal: Type: *Callimerus tenuissimus* Corp., 1925” (NHML, ♂). **Paratypes** of *C. tenuissimus*. “Paratype / Gopaldhara, Rungbong V y., Darjiling, H. Stevens, VI.20 / H. Stevens. Brit. Mus. 1922-307 / J.B. Corporaal: Paratype: *Callimerus tenuissimus* Corp., 1925” (NHML, 1♂); “Gopaldhara, Nepal-Sikkim Frontier, H. Stevens, 1919 / Figurae II, 6, Typus / 1925. from Brit. Mus. / J.B. Corporaal: Type: Paratype: *Callimerus tenuissimus* Corp., 1925 / *Callimerus tenuissimus* Corporaal, 1926 ZMAN type COLE. 1727. 1” (ZMAN, 1♂). **Holotype** of *C. nigripes*. “Gopaldhara, Nepal-Sikkim Frontier, H. Stevens / H. Stevens. Brit. Mus. 1922-307 / J.B. Corporaal: Type: *Callimerus tenuissimus* Corp. var. *nigripes* Corp., 1925” (NHML, ♀); **Paratype** of *C. nigripes*. “Gopaldhara, Nepal-Sikkim Frontier, H. Stevens, 1919 / Figurae II, 7, Typus / 1925. from Brit. Mus. / J.B. Corporaal: Type: Paratype: *Callimerus tenuissimus* Corp. var. *nigripes* Corp., 1925 / *Callimerus nigripes* Corporaal, 1926 ZMAN type COLE. 1728. 1” (ZMAN, 1♀).

Other material examined. **India:** “62024 / Doherty / Assam, Nagas / Fry Coll. 1905. 100 / *C. elegans* Gorham / *Callimerus elegans* Gorham, Gorham det. / *Callimerus elegans* Gorham, Assam” (NHML, 1♂).

FIGURE 1. *Callimerus tenuissimus* Corporaal, 1926: A, B holotype of *C. tenuissimus* C, D paratypes of *C. tenuissimus* E, F holotype of *C. tenuissimus* var. *nigripes*.

FIGURE 2. Male terminalia of *Callimerus tenuissimus* Corporaal, 1926: A holotype, tegmen in dry condition B–G from Assam, photoed in ethyl acetate.

Diagnosis. This species is readily recognized by its elytral pattern formed by white scales: each elytron with a short vitta behind scutellum; five spots of ground plan are present, but lateral spot shifted anteriorly adjacent to subbasal spot, and subapical spot modified into a transverse fascia (Fig. 1). It is distinguished from *C. angustior* by having a short vitta behind scutellum, a transverse fascia in apical third, apices of parameres without hooks, and male abdominal ventrite VIII without prolonged lateral lobes.

Supplemental description. *Male terminalia:* tergite VIII rectangular, longer than wide, posterior corners gently rounded; sternite VIII broadly and shallowly emarginate apically; apices of parameres without denticles, dorsal surface of tegmen with an additional cordate transparent region.

Variation. The color of the legs has variations. In the specimens examined, the legs of female specimens are all black with the coxae and the extreme base of femora yellow; the legs of males are dominantly yellow with an apical portion of metafemora and the whole metatibiae and metatarsi black. The variation may be correlated with sex as suggested by Corporaal (1939).

Comment on synonymy. When erected the species, Corporaal (1926) stated that *C. tenuissimus* var. *nigripes* might prove to be the females of *C. tenuissimus* as they were only different on the color of their legs; and later he confirmed his idea by identifying their sexes and then made the two names synonyms (Corporaal, 1939, pl. 1, figs 11a, 11b). However, *C. nigripes* was misplaced under *C. prasinatus* Lewis as a synonym in the catalogue (Löbl *et al.* 2007: 371). After examining all the type series, I agree with Corporaal's comment that *C. nigripes* and *C. tenuissimus* are synonymous.

Distribution. India (Darjeeling, Assam).

Callimerus angustior Pic, 1927

Figs 3, 4, 18A, 19

angustior Pic, 1927: 9 (*Callimerus*; type locality: Tonkin); Corporaal & Pic 1940: 192 (*Stenocallimerus*).

Type material examined. **Lectotype** designated herein: “Tonkin; Chapa, 12.V.1918; Jeanvoine / Type / *Callimerus angustior* n. sp. / Museum Paris, Coll. M. Pic / Type / Lectotype: *Callimerus angustior* Pic, 1927, des. Yang G.Y., 2011” (MNHN, ♀).

Note on type material. Lectotype is designated herein as the name-bearing type was not fixed in the original publication.

Other material examined. **China: Guangxi:** China, Guangxi, Jinxiu, Dayaoshan, Luoyingou, 1100 m, 2017.V-07, J.T. Zhao leg. (CCCC, 1♀); **Vietnam:** “Tonkin, Chapa, 23.VI.1918, Jeanvoine / var / *angustior* Pic/communique M Pic / [...] *C. tenuissimus* Corp. / Corporaal Vid 1939 / Museum Paris, Coll. M. Pic” (MNHN, 1♂); “Tam Dao, Vinh Phu Prov., N. Vietnam, 4-V-1996, Y. Arita leg.” (MNHN, 1♂); **Laos:** “Laos, Luang Prabang Prov., 1934'N/10213'E, Ban Kiukacham env., 1400-1450 m, 19.vi.2009, M. Geiser & D. Hauck leg. / NHMB Basel, NMPC Prague Laos 2009 expedition: M. Brancucci, M. Geiser, Z. Kraus, D. Hauck, V. Kuban” (NHMB, 1♀); Ban Saleui, Houa Phan, Laos, 01.05.2012, X. Gouverneur (Coll. Xavier, 1♀).

Diagnosis. This species is readily recognized by its elytral pattern of white scales. Each elytron with five round spots: a subbasal spot at basal fifth, a lateral spot close to elytral margin at basal third, a median spot near suture, a subapical spot close to elytral margin at apical third, and an apical spot. It can be distinguished from *C. tenuissimus* by the absence of a short vitta behind scutellum, and by subapical spot rounded, apex of parameres with an evident denticle on ventral surface, and male abdominal ventrite VIII with prolonged lateral lobes (Fig. 4G); and from *C. maderi* by having five spots on each elytron and male abdominal sternite VIII with prolonged lateral lobes.

Supplemental description. *Male terminalia:* tergite VIII inverted trapezoidal, length nearly equal to width, apical margin straight, with a weak median protrusion; sternite VIII with a pair of lateral lobes, as long as the length of sternite VIII along midline; apex of each paramere with an evident denticle on ventral surface.

Distribution. Vietnam, China (Guangxi), Laos. Newly recorded from China and Laos.

FIGURE 3. *Callimerus angustior* Pic, 1927: **A, B** lectotype **C** a specimen from type locality, with elytral spots smaller than those of lectotype **D** ground plan of elytral scales.

FIGURE 4. Male terminalia of *Callimerus angustior* Pic, 1927, from type locality: **A–C** tegmen (**A** dorsal view **B** lateral view **C** ventral view) **D** phallus **E** spicular fork **F** tergite VIII **G** sternite VIII.

***Callimerus maderi* Corporaal, 1939**

Figs 5A–C, 6, 19

maderi Corporaal, 1939: 189 (*Callimerus*; type locality: Tien-mu-shan); Corporaal & Pic 1940: 190 (*Callimerus* (*Stenocallimerus*)); – Corporaal 1950: 83 (*Stenocallimerus*); Xie & Zhang 1993: 30 (Jiangxi); Kolibáč 1998: 176 (*Callimerus*).

Type material examined. **Lectotype** designated herein: “Tienmuschan, N. W. China Rtt./Suenson legit/Leopold Mader don. 1939/J. B. Corporaal: Holotype: *Callimerus maderi* Corp., 1939, ♂/Coll. Zoologisch Museum Amsterdam/*Callimerus maderi* Corporaal, 1939, ZMAN type 2194.1/♀” (ZMAN, ♀); **Paralectotype**: 5 ex., “Tienmuschan, N. W. China Rtt./Suenson legit/Leopold Mader don. 1939/J. B. Corporaal: Paratype: *Callimerus maderi* Corp., 1939, ♂/Coll. Zoologisch Museum Amsterdam/*Callimerus maderi* Corporaal, 1939, ZMAN type 2194.2/♀” (ZMAN, 1♀); “8.6.36, O. Piel, coll./T’ienmu-Shan, Musée Heude/C. 8/J. B. Corporaal: Paratype: *Callimerus maderi* Corp., 1939, ♂/*Callimerus maderi* Corporaal, 1939, ZMAN type 2194.3/♀” (ZMAN, 1♀); “25.6.36, O. Piel, coll./T’ienmu-Shan, Musée Heude/C. 8/J. B. Corporaal: Paratype: *Callimerus maderi* Corp., 1939, ♂/*Callimerus maderi* Corporaal, 1939, ZMAN type 2194.4/♀” (ZMAN, 1♀); “20.VII.36, O. Piel, coll./T’ienmu-Shan, Musée Heude/C. 8/J. B. Corporaal: Paratype: *Callimerus maderi* Corp., 1939, ♂/*Callimerus maderi* Corporaal, 1939, ZMAN type 2194.5/♀” (ZMAN, 1♀); “22.VII.36, O. Piel, coll./T’ienmu-Shan, Musée Heude/C. 8/J. B. Corporaal: Paratype: *Callimerus maderi* Corp., 1939, ♀/*Callimerus maderi* Corporaal, 1939, ZMAN type 2194.6/♀” (ZMAN, 1♀).

Note on type material. Lectotype is designated herein as the name-bearing type was not fixed in the original publication, though a holotype label was pinned to the type specimen.

Other material examined. **China: Zhejiang:** “20.VII.36, O. Piel, coll./T’ienmu-Shan, Musée Heude/ IOZ(E) 1124817” (IZAS, 1♀); same data but IOZ(E)1124818 (IZAS, 1♀); same data but IOZ(E) 1124819 (IZAS, 1♂); 22.VII.36, O. Piel, coll./T’ienmu-Shan, Musée Heude/IOZ(E) 1124813 (IZAS, 1♀); 24.VII.36, O. Piel, coll./T’ienmu-Shan, Musée Heude/ IOZ(E)1124815 (IZAS, 1♀); 28.VII.36, O. Piel, coll./T’ienmu-Shan, Musée Heude/C. 8/ IOZ(E)1124820 (IZAS, 1♀); “Tienmuschan, N. W. China Rtt.”; Coll. Frey (NHMB, 1); “Tienmuschan, N. W. China Rtt./*Callimerus maderi* Cor., Mit Paratypus verglichen”; Coll. Frey (NHMB, 1); “T’ienmu-Shan, Musée Heude/24.7.36, O. Piel, coll./IOZ(E)1124814” (IZAS, 1♀); “T’ienmu-Shan, Musée Heude/24.7.36, O. Piel, coll./IOZ(E)1124816” (IZAS, 1♀); **China: Zhejiang Prov., Lin’an City, West Tianmushan, alt 1200 m, 15-VII-2008, TANG Liang & He W J leg. (SNUC, 2♂♂ 2♀♀);** Tienmushan, July 12.1936, IOZ(E)1124833 (IZAS, 1♂); Tienmushan, July 12.1937, IOZ(E)1124835 (IZAS, 1♀); Tienmushan, July 12.1937, IOZ(E)1124836 (IZAS, 1♀); Tienmushan, July 14.1937, IOZ(E)1124837 (IZAS, 1♀); Tienmushan, July 20.1936, IOZ(E)1124828 (IZAS, 1♂); Tienmushan, July 24.1936, IOZ(E)1124821 (IZAS, 1♂); Tienmushan, July 4.1936, IOZ(E)1124829 (IZAS, 1♀); Tienmushan, July 4.1936, IOZ(E)1124831 (IZAS, 1♀); Tienmushan, July 8.1936, IOZ(E)1124822 (IZAS, 1♀); Tienmushan, July 8.1936, IOZ(E)1124823 (IZAS, 1♂); Tienmushan, July 8.1936, IOZ(E)1124824 (IZAS, 1♂); Tienmushan, July 8.1936, IOZ(E)1124825 (IZAS, 1♀); Tienmushan, July 8.1936, IOZ(E)1124826 (IZAS, 1♀); Tienmushan, July 8.1936, IOZ(E)1124827 (IZAS, 1♀); Tienmushan, July 8.1936, IOZ(E)1124832 (IZAS, 1♀); Tienmushan, July 9.1936, IOZ(E)1124834 (IZAS, 1♀); Tienmushan, 3.9.1947, IOZ(E)1124838 (IZAS, 1♀); Tienmushan, 3.9.1947, IOZ(E)1124839 (IZAS, 1♂); Tienmushan, 1957.VI.28 (IZAS, 1♂); Three Li Pavilion, Tienmushan, 1957.VI.27, IOZ(E)1124626 (IZAS, 1♂); Tienmushan, YANG Jikun leg., 1957-VI-28 (CAU, 1♀); Mt. Longwang, Anji County, 1995-VIII-10, 500 m, WU Hong leg. (IZAS, 1♂); Mt. Longwang, Anji County, 500 m, 1996-VI-12, YANG Xingke leg. (IZAS, 1♀); **Fujian:** 2012-08-02, Lipin, Tongmu Village, Wuyi Mountains, Song Haitian leg. (CYGY, 2 ex.); **Jiangxi:** Jinggangshan, 2008.VII., Meng Zehong leg. (GZU, 2♂♂); Gu Ling, 4.7.35, O. Piel, coll., IOZ(E)1124841 (IZAS, 1♀); **Hunan:** Niujiaolong, Taoyuandong Reserve, Shidu town, Yanling county, 1265 m, 2008.VII.5, YANG Ganyan leg., on broadleaf bamboo *Indocalamus* near creek, IOZ(E)1890854 (IZAS, 1♂1♀); Road to Shennong Fall, Taoyuandong Reserve, Shidu town, Yanling county, 868 m, 2008.VII.7, sweep net, LI Yingchao (IZAS, 1♂); Guizhizhai, Mangshan Forest Park, Yizhang county, 1271 m, 2008.VII.14, sweep net, CHEN fuqiang (IZAS, 1♂); same data but collected by ZHU Xiaoyu (IZAS, 1♀); **Guangdong:** Qingshigu, Nan Mountains, Ruyuan county, 831 m, 2008.VII.21, LIANG Hongbin leg. IOZ(E)1890855 (IZAS, 1♂); **Guangxi:** Shili Great valley, Gaozai Village, Xing’an county, 2007-VI-6, YANG Ganyan, sweep net (CYGY, 1♀); Huilong Temple, Maoer Mountain, 2012-VII-24, 1600-1100

m, BI Wenxuan leg. (CBWX, 1♂).

FIGURE 5. A–C *Callimerus maderi* Corporaal, 1939 (A, B lectotype C topotype) D–F *Callimerus micans* Corporaal & Pic, 1940 D, E syntype, elytral scales indistinct F from Pianma, elytral scales distinct.

FIGURE 6. Male terminalia of *Callimerus maderi* Corporaal, 1939, from type locality: A–C tegmen (A dorsal view B lateral view C ventral view) D phallus E spicular fork F tergite VIII G sternite VIII.

Diagnosis. This species is readily recognized by three white spots on each elytron: a subbasal spot at basal fifth near suture, a subapical spot at apical third near margin, and an apical spot. It is distinguished from *C. angustior* by elytron lacking median and lateral spots, and male abdominal sternite VIII simply emarginate apically, without prolonged lateral lobes. It differs from *C. micans* in having a round spot at basal fifth; short median vitta absent; subapically with round spot, not transverse fascia; male tergite VIII straight or insignificantly emarginate at middle apically; dorsal sinus of tegmen 3.5 times the length of paramere length.

Supplemental description. *Legs:* yellow; outer surface of pro- and mesofemora, apical half of metafemora black; outer surface of tibiae and dorsal surface of tarsi black. *Male terminalia:* tergite VIII quadrate, posterior margin nearly straight, or in some specimens insignificantly emarginate at middle; sternite VIII emarginate at apex; apex of each paramere with a triangular denticle projecting outward; ventral surface of tegmen with a long broad heart-shaped transparent membranous region.

Distribution. China (Zhejiang, Fujian, Jiangxi, Hunan, Guangdong, Guangxi).

Callimerus micans Corporaal & Pic, 1940

Figs 5D–F, 7, 19

micans Corporaal & Pic, 1940: 190 [*Callimerus* (*Stenocallimerus*); type locality: “N. E. Burma”]; Corporaal 1950: 83 (*Stenocallimerus*); Xie & Zhang 1993: 30 (Guangxi, China, based on wrong identification).

Type material examined. Syntype. “N. E. Burma, Kambaiti, 2000 m, 17/5.1934, Malaise / Paratype: *Stenocallimerus micans* Corp. & Pic / *Stenocallimerus micans* Corporaal & Pic, 1940, ZMAN type COLE. 1726. 1” (ZMAN, 1♀).

Other material examined. China: Yunnan: Tengchong Count., Houqiao town, Guyong Forestry Farm, 2584 m, 2006.V.27, leg. LIANG Hongbin (IZAS, 2♂♂4♀♀); Tengchong Count., north to Jietou town 0.7 km, 1560 m, 2006.5.22, leg. LIANG Hongbin (IZAS, 1♂); Pianma Town, Lushui County, Nujiang, Yunnan, 2100 m, 2020.V.25–30, XU Hao & WANG Chengbin leg. (CYGY, 1♂).

Diagnosis. Each elytron with three white scale patches: a short median longitudinal vitta, a transverse fascia at apical fourth, and an apical spot. It is distinguished from *C. maderi* by elytron having a short median longitudinal vitta; subbasal spot absent; subapically with transverse fascia, not round spot; male abdominal tergite VIII rounded apically and tegmen with dorsal sinus 2.2 times the length of parameres.

Supplemental description. *Male terminalia:* tergite VIII trapezoidal, length nearly equal to width, posterior margin rounded; sternite VIII with a semicircular emargination apically; parameres convergent, each apex with an outward-directed denticle; dorsal sinus deeper than ventral sinus, dorsal sinus 2.2 times the length of parameres, ventral sinus 1.6 times the length of parameres; dorsal and ventral membranous region absent, lateral membranous regions present; phallobasic apodeme 0.4 times the length of tegmen.

Variation. The examined syntype with legs yellow proximally and black distally (1♀). Specimens from Tengchong with legs either yellow proximally and black distally (2♀♀) or entirely yellow (3♂♂, 2♀♀), and specimen from Pianma with legs entirely yellow (1♂). Leg coloration varies independently of sex.

Remarks. The syntype of *C. micans* (female, ZMAN) and specimens from Houqiao and Jietou are in poor condition, with elytral scales partially abraded. Although the female syntype cannot be dissected, males from Houqiao, Jietou, and Pianma were examined and proved conspecific. Their assignment to *C. micans* is supported by overall morphological similarity and by their geographic proximity to the type locality, as Houqiao lies in the same border region as the Kambaiti Pass, separated only by the international boundary. The syntype shows a subapical fascia and an apical spot, though the original description mentioned only the apical spot. Houqiao specimens additionally bear a faint median spot, while Pianma specimens, in good condition, clearly exhibit a short median longitudinal vitta, a subapical fascia, and an apical spot. Thus, the characteristic elytral pattern of *C. micans* consists of a median vitta, a subapical fascia, and an apical spot, although these may be obscure in worn specimens.

The record from Guangxi (Xie & Zhang 1993; from Chang 1988) represents a misidentification, as the specimen examined by Chang belongs to *C. angustatus* based on the male genitalia.

Distribution. Myanmar (Kachin), China (Yunnan).

FIGURE 7. Male terminalia of *Callimerus micans* Corporaal & Pic, 1940, from type locality: **A–C** tegmen (**A** dorsal view **B**, **B1** ventral view **C** apex of paramere) **D** phallus **E** spicular fork **F** tergite VIII **G** sternite VIII.

Callimerus angustatus Pic, 1939

Figs 8A–C, 9, 19

angustatus Pic, 1939: 19 (*Callimerus*; type locality: Tonkin); Corporaal & Pic 1940: 192 (*Stenocallimerus*).

Type material examined. **Lectotype** designated herein: “Mt. Mauson, Tonkin; H. Perrot / *Callimerus angustatus* n. sp. [hw. by Pic]/communiqué (coll. Pic)/Muséum Paris, Coll. M. Pic/Type” (MNHN, ♂; dissected).

Note on type material. Lectotype is designated herein as the name-bearing type was not fixed in the original publication.

Other material examined. **Vietnam:** “Tam Dao, Vinh Phu Prov., N. Vietnam, 1-V-1996, Y. Okushima leg.” (MNHN, 2♂♂ 1♀); **China: Guizhou:** Zunyi Pref., Suiyang Count., Kuankuoshui reserve, 2010.VI.3, leg. WANG Zhiliang, 1400–1500m (IZAS, 3♂♂); same data but 2010.VI.5 (IZAS, 3♂♂ 1♀); same data but leg. LIU Wangang, 2010.VI.4, 1450–1515 m, near a reservoir (IZAS, 2♂♂); same data but 2010.VI.5, near a tea factory (IZAS, 1♂ 1♀); Heiwanhe, Mount Fanjing, 1200 m, SONG Qiongzhang, 2002.VI.2 (GZU, 1♀); Huguosi to liuxuling, Mount Fanjing, 2008.VII.17, LIU Ye leg. (IZAS, 1♀; GZU, 1♀); Mount Fanjing, Jiangkou county, 2008.VI.30. 1600 m, CHOU Wen-I leg. (CCCC, 1♂); Gan Chouen fou, Anshunfu; P. Caralerie 1912 (MNHN, 1♂); “China, W Guizhou prov., Leigongshan, Xijiang, 29 May–2 Jun 1997, 1200–1900 m, Bolm lgt.” (NHMB, 21, sex unknown); **Guangxi:** Jinxiu Count., Shengtang Mountain, 900–1900 m, 2000.VI.29, YAO Jian (IZAS, 1♂); Wuming Count., Daming Mountain, leg. YANG Jikun, 1963-V-23, *Stenocallimerus micans* Corp. & Pic, det. by CHANG Yujun (CAU, 1♂); **Hainan:** Wuzhishan, 2011-IV-16, 1600 m, BI Wenxuan leg. (CBWX, ♂); Wuzhishan, 2009.IV.9, 708–1206 m, leg. LIN Meiyang, by beating (IZAS, 2♂♂).

FIGURE 8. A–C *Callimerus angustatus* Pic, 1939 (A, B lectotype C a specimen from Guizhou with apical spot), D, E holotype of *Callimerus apicalis* Pic, 1954.

FIGURE 9. Male terminalia of *Callimerus angustatus* Pic, 1939, lectotype: A–C tegmen (A dorsal view B lateral view C ventral view C1 apex of paramere) D phallus E spicular fork F tergite VIII G sternite VIII.

Diagnosis. This species has white scales forming an apical spot in well preserved specimens. However, these scales may be partially abraded or indefinite in some specimens. It is distinguished from *C. apicalis* by metafemoral inner surface yellow; male abdominal sternite VIII with prolonged lateral lobes (equal to the length of sternite VIII along midline); dorsal sinus of tegmen slightly longer than ventral sinus; membranous region on ventral surface of tegmen very small, distinctly shorter than paramere length.

Supplemental description. *Legs:* yellow, distal 1/5–1/2 of metafemoral outer surface black; tibiae entirely yellow, or with outer surface partly or entirely black. *Male terminalia:* tergite VIII rectangular, longer than wide, apical margin slightly convex; sternite VIII with a pair of lateral lobes, as long as sternite VIII along median line; apex of each paramere with a subapical denticle on ventrolateral surface; dorsal sinus of tegmen slightly longer than ventral sinus; membranous region on ventral surface of tegmen very small, distinctly shorter than paramere length.

Distribution. Vietnam, China (Guizhou, Guangxi, Hainan). Newly recorded from China.

Callimerus apicalis Pic, 1954

Figs 8D–E, 10

apicalis Pic, 1954b: 61 (*Callimerus*; type locality: China); Xie & Zhang 1993: 30 (*Stenocallimerus*).

Type material examined. Holotype by monotypy: “NHRS-JLKB 000020256/Kuatun, Fukien, China, 6.7.46 (Tschung sen.)/Type: *Callimerus apicalis*, det. Pic, n. sp.” (NHRS, ♂, dissected).

Other material examined. China: Guangxi: Jinxiu County, Shengtang Mountain, beating on bamboo, N23.9688 E110.1172, 1170 m, 2025.VII.18, YANG Ganyan leg. (CYGY, 1♂); same locality, 2025.VII.19, XIE Guanglin leg. (CYGY, 1♀); same locality, 2025.VII.13, SHI Hongliang leg. (CYGY, 1 ex.); Yong’an village, Xing’an county, 2006.VII (CYGY, 1♂); Huilong Temple, Mao’er Mountain, 2012-VII-24, 1600–1100 m, BI Wenxuan leg. (CBWX, ♂).

FIGURE 10. Male terminalia of *Callimerus apicalis* Pic, 1954, holotype: A–C tegmen (A dorsal view B lateral view C ventral view A1 apex of paramere) D phallus E spicular fork F tergite VIII G sternite VIII.

Diagnosis. This species can be distinguished from *C. angustatus* by inner surface of apical half of metafemora black; male abdominal sternite VIII simply emarginate at apex, without prolonged lateral lobes; dorsal sinus deep, extending almost to base of phallobase and twice the length of ventral sinus; membranous region on ventral surface of tegmen large, its length equal to paramere length.

Supplemental description. *Legs:* yellow; outer surface of apical half of pro- and mesofemora black; apical half of metafemora black; outer surface of tibiae (in some specimens also the inner surface of basal half, or even the entire metatibiae) black; dorsal surface of tarsi mostly black. *Male terminalia:* tergite VIII rectangular, longer than wide, apical margin faintly emarginate at middle; sternite VIII deeply emarginate apically; parameres divergent, each apex with a small denticle; dorsal sinus deep, extending almost to internal limit and twice the length of ventral sinus; membranous region on ventral surface of tegmen large, equal in length to the paramere.

Distribution. China (Fujian, Guangxi).

Callimerus koenigi Pic, 1954

Figs 11, 12, 20

koenigi Pic, 1954a: 58 [*Callimerus* (*Stenocallimerus*); type locality: “Kuatun”, Fukien].

subattenuatus Pic, 1954a: 59 (*Callimerus* (*Stenocallimerus*) *koenigi* var.; type locality: “Kuatun”, Fukien). **syn. nov.**

taiwanus Miyatake, 1965b: 159, pl. 1, figs. 3, 4 (*Callimerus*; type locality: “Oiwake-Tattaka, C. Formosa”); Murakami 2025: 104 (Ishigaki-jima and Iriomote-jima, Okinawa Pref., Japan). **syn. nov.**

Type material examined. **Holotype of *C. koenigi*:** “Kuatun, Fukien, China, 8.6.[19]46, Tschung Sen/Type: *Callimerus koenigi* n. sp., det. Pic/NHRS-JLKB, 000020258” (NHRS, ♀); **Paratype of *C. koenigi*:** 5♀♀, “Kuatun, Fukien, China, 8.6.[19]46, (Tschung Sen.)/ *Callimerus* (*Stenocallimerus*) *koenigi* n. sp./[...]/Museum Paris, Coll. M. Pic/Type/♀/Paratype: *Callimerus* (*Stenocallimerus*) *koenigi* Pic, 1954; det. YANG G.Y., 2011” (MNHN, 1♀); “Kuatun, Fukien, China, 8.6.[19]46, Leg. Tschung Sen/Paratype: *Callimerus koenigi* Pic, det. Pic/♀” (NHMB, 1♀); “Kuatun, Fukien, China, 14.5.[19]46, leg. Tschung-Sen/*Stenocallimerus koenigi* Pic[hw. by Pic]/*Stenocallimerus* Corp. & Pic/Museum Paris, Coll. M. Pic/♀” (MNHN, 1♀); “Kuatun, Fukien, China, 15.6.[19]46, leg. Tschung-Sen/Museum Paris, Coll. M. Pic/♀” (MNHN, 1♀); “Kuatun, Fukien, China, 15.6.[19]46, leg. Tschung-Sen/Klapperichi Pic/Museum Paris, Coll. M. Pic/♀” (MNHN, 1♀); **Holotype of *C. subattenuatus*:** “Kuatun, Fukien, China, 14.5.[19]46, leg. Tschung-Sen/var./Museum Paris, Coll. M. Pic/Holotype: *Callimerus* (*Stenocallimerus*) *koenigi* var. *subattenuatus* Pic, 1954; det. YANG G.Y., 2011/♂” (MNHN, ♂).

Other material examined. **China: Zhejiang:** West Tianmu Mountains, Lin’an, 2008.VI, Huang Hao leg. (SNUC, 2♂); **Fujian:** Pikeng, Wuyishan, 1100 m, 1997.V.21, Collector: Wang Jiashe (IZAS, 1♂); Longqishan, Jiangle County, 1991.V.19, Zhang Runzhi (IZAS, 1♂); Long Qishan, Jiangle County, 1991.V.18, Li Wenzhu leg. (IZAS, 1♀); Guilin Village, Huangkeng township, Jianyang County, 270-590 m, 1960. IV.7, Zhang Yiran leg., IOZ(E)1124870 (IZAS, 1♀); Guilin Village, Huangkeng township, Jianyang County, 270-590 m, 1960.IV.7, Jiang Shengqiao leg., IOZ(E)1124871 (IZAS, 1♀); Dazhulan to Xianfeng Peak, Huangkeng township, Jianyang County, 950-1170 m, 1960.V.2, Zhang Yiran leg., IOZ(E)1124873 (IZAS, 1♂); Aotou Village, Huangkeng township, Jianyang County, 900-950 m, 1960.V.3, Pu Fuji, IOZ(E)1124866 (IZAS, 1♂); same locality, 800-950 m, 1960.VI.3, Collector: Zuo Yong, IOZ(E)1124869 (IZAS, 1♂); same locality, 750-950 m, 1960.V.6, Collector: Zhang Yiran, IOZ(E)1124872 (IZAS, 1♀); same locality, 720-950 m, 1960.IV.30, collected by: Zhang Yiran, IOZ(E)1124868 (IZAS, 1♀); same locality, 700-950 m, 1960.IV.30, Pu Fuji, IOZ(E) 1124865 (IZAS, 1♂); same locality, 700-950 m, 1960.IV.23, Pufuji, IOZ(E)1124867 (IZAS, 1♀); same locality, 700-900 m (IZAS, 1♂); Fujian, 1948.VI.10, IOZ(E)1124863 (IZAS, 1♂); Fujian Longyan, Meihuashan N.R., Guihe, 1200 m, 4-VI-2007, Huang Hao leg. (SNUC, 2♀♀); “Kuatun, Fukien, China, 15.6.[19]46, leg. Tschung-Sen/Museum Paris, Coll. M. Pic/♀” (MNHN, 1♀); “Kuatun, Fukien, China, 15.6.[19]46, leg. Tschung-Sen/Klapperichi Pic/Museum Paris, Coll. M. Pic/♀” (MNHN, 1♀); “Kuatun, Fukien, China, 14.5.[19]46, leg. Tschung-Sen/*Stenocallimerus koenigi* Pic[hw by Pic]/*Stenocallimerus* Corp. et Pic/Museum Paris, Coll. M. Pic/♀” (MNHN, 1♀); **Taiwan:** La-la Shan, Taoyuan County, 1999.V.12, CHOU Wen-I leg. (CCCC, 1♂); La-la Shan, Taoyuan County, 1999.V.12, CHOU Wen-i leg. (CCCC,

1♀); Ninglao village, Chiensih township, Hsinchu County, 1400 m, 2008.IV.27 (CCCC, 3♀♀); Cinsbu, Miaoli County, 2009.V.5, CHOU Wen-i leg. (CCCC, 1♀); Suyan, 1996.IV.17, CHOU Wen-i leg. (CCCC, 1♀); (Near Meifeng) Nantou Formosa, 2. May 1976, Coll. T. Shimomura (MNHN, 3♂♂2♀♀); (Near Meifeng) Nantou Formosa, 18. May 1976, Coll. T. Shimomura (MNHN, 1♀); (Near Meifeng) Nantou Hsien, Taiwan, May 14th, 1978, Coll. T. Shimomura (MNHN, 1♀); Nr. Szuyuan, 1950-2350 m, Taichung Pref. Taiwan, 1-IV-1982, T. Shimomura leg. (MNHN, 1♀); **Guangxi:** Hongmaochong, Huaping, 1963.VI.11, YANG Jikun leg. (CAU, 1♂); Jinzhong Highway, Jinxiu, 1100 m, 1999.V.10, YANG Xingke leg. (IZAS, 1♀); Luoyingou, Dayao Mountain, Jinxiu, 1200 m, 2016.IV.18, foliage, Zhao Jinteng leg. (CCCC, 1♂); Xinpingtun, Dayaoshan, Jinxiu, 1000 m, 2016.IV.27, net, ZHAO Jinteng leg. (CCCC, 1♀). **Japan:** “Mt. Omoto-dake, Ishigaki Isand, Okinawa, Japan, 18.IV.2010, N. & T. Ohbayashi leg.” (CYGY, 1♂3♀♀); same data but 19.IV.2010 (CYGY, 1♀); same data but 20.IV.2010 (CYGY, 2♂♂).

FIGURE 11. *Callimerus koenigi* Pic, 1954 (A holotype of *C. koenigi* B one of the paratype of *C. koenigi*, showing the scattered scales on elytra C holotype of *Callimerus (Stenocallimerus) koenigi* var. *subattenuatus*).

Diagnosis. Males can be readily recognized by the specialized structure of terminal abdominal segments; females can be distinguished from *C. prasinatus* by elytra with scattered scales over entire surface. Some females with abraded scales are difficult to identify.

Supplemental description. *Elytra:* integument metallic green, blue, or piceous, in some specimens partially and weakly brown in disc and lateral (Fig. 11C); with scales scattered over entire surface. *Legs:* fulvous, sometimes tibiae and tarsi darker. *Male terminalia:* male abdominal terminal segments highly specialized: tergite VIII swollen into two hemispheres with bluntly pointed apices; sternite VIII sclerotized and apically bifurcate, and tightly joined to tergite VIII; sternite VII deeply and broadly emarginate and with a bifurcate projection at middle of the emargination; apices of parameres tapering; ventral surface of tegmen with a small membranous region.

FIGURE 12. Male terminalia of *Callimerus koenigi* Pic, 1954, from type locality Fujian: **A–C** tegmen (**A** dorsal view **B** lateral view **C** ventral view) **D, D1** phallus **E** spicular fork **F, F1, F2** tergite VIII **G** sternite VIII.

Comment on synonymy. The holotype and paratypes of *C. koenigi* Pic, 1954 are all females, and the holotype of *C. koenigi* var. *subattenuatus* Pic, 1954 is a male. The latter taxon differs from *C. koenigi* only in the integumental color of the elytra, which is piceous and somewhat lighter or brownish at the elytral base (dark blue in the type series of *C. koenigi*). Both taxa bear scattered scales over the elytra. Based on overall morphological characters and our knowledge of the local fauna, I treat these two taxa as synonyms. Although the holotype of *C. koenigi* var. *subattenuatus* Pic, 1954 was not dissected, its exposed abdominal apex revealed its specific characters. *Callimerus taiwanus* Miyatake, 1965 is also synonymized with *C. koenigi* based on its original descriptions of external characters as well as detailed examination of male terminalia. *Callimerus taiwanus* is undoubtedly conspecific with *C. koenigi* Pic, 1954 due to its unusual and highly recognizable male terminal abdominal segments.

Distribution. China (Zhejiang, Fujian, Taiwan, Guangxi), Japan (Okinawa).

***Callimerus prasinatus* Lewis, 1896**

Figs 13, 14, 20

prasinatus Lewis, 1896: 338 (*Callimerus*; type locality: “Oshima”, Japan); Corporaal & Pic 1940: 190 [*Callimerus* (*Stenocallimerus*)]; Corporaal 1950: 83 (*Stenocallimerus*); Xie & Zhang 1993: 30 (China); Kolibáč 1998: 176 (*Callimerus*).

bicoloripes Pic, 1925: 32 (*Callimerus*; type locality: “Formose”); Corporaal & Pic 1940: 190 [*Callimerus* (*Stenocallimerus*)]; Corporaal 1950: 83 (*Stenocallimerus*). **syn. nov.**

sauteri Corporaal & Pic, 1940: 192 [*Callimerus* (*Stenocallimerus*) *bicoloripes* var.; type locality: “Formose”]; Corporaal 1950: 83 (*Stenocallimerus bicoloripes* var.); Nakane 1996: 135 (*Stenocallimerus*; raised to species rank). **syn. nov.**

okinawanus Yajima & Nakane, 1969: 5 (*Stenocallimerus*; type locality: “Hentona, Is. Okinawa”); Murakami 2025 (synonymized with *C. prasinatus*).

FIGURE 13. *Callimerus prasinatus* Lewis, 1896 (A, B lectotype of *C. prasinatus* C, D lectotype of *C. bicoloripes* E, F lectotype of *C. bicoloripes* var. *sauteri* G–L females from Taiwan showing transition in color of legs).

Type material examined. Lectotype of *C. prasinatus* (designated by Kolibáč, 1998): “Archipel, Liou-Kiou, Ile d’Oshima, Ferrié 1895/Museum Paris, Coll. M. Pic/Syntype/Lectotypus: *Callimerus prasinatus* Lewis, 1896, ♀, Jiri Kolibac - 1998” (MNHN, ♀; Figs 13A, B); **Paralectotypes of *C. prasinatus*:** 6 ex., “Archipel, Liou-Kiou, Ile d’Oshima, Ferrié 1895/prasinatus Lewis/Callimerus prasinatus, Lew., Co-type[hw, by Gorham]/Museum Paris; Coll. H.S. Gorham

1911/Type/♂/Syntype: *Callimerus prasinatus* Lewis, 1896; ♂; det. YANG G.Y., 2011” (MNHN, 1♂); “Archipel, Liou-Kiou, Ile d’Oshima, Ferrié 1895/*Callimerus prasinatus*, Cotype! Lewis/Museum Paris, ex. Coll. R. Oberthür/Type[printed]/♀” (MNHN, ♀); “Archipel, Liou-Kiou, Ile d’Oshima, Ferrié 1895/*Callimerus prasinatus*, Lewis, ex type/Museum Paris, ex. Coll. R. Oberthür/Type[printed]” (MNHN, 1♀); “Archipel, Liou-Kiou, Ile d’Oshima, Ferrié 1895/Museum Paris, Coll. M. Pic/Syntype[printed]/Paralectotype: *Callimerus prasinatus* Lewis, 1896, ♀, Jiri Kolibac-1998” (MNHN, 1♀); “Archipel, Liou-Kiou, Ile d’Oshima, Ferrié 1895/Type/*Callimerus prasinatus* Lewis, Type/♂” (NHML, 1♂); “Archipel, Liou-Kiou, Ile d’Oshima, Ferrié 1895/*Callimerus prasinatus* Lewis, Cotype, ex. MUs R. Oberthür/*Callimerus prasinatus* Lewis, 1896, ZMAN type 2195.1/♀” (ZMAN, 1♀). **Lectotype of *C. bicoloripes*** designated herein: “Taiwan, Formosa, IV/*Callimers* sp./*bicoloripes* [hw. By Pic]/ *Stenocallimerus* Corp. & Pic/type [hw. By Pic]/*Callimerus* nov. spec. [hw. By Schenkling]/*Corporaal* vid, 1939/det. J.B. Corporaal 1939: *Callimerus prasinatus* Lewis ab. *Bicoloripes* Pic/Museum Paris, Col. M. Pic/Type [printed]/Lectotype: ♀, *Callimerus bicoloripes* Pic, 1925; des. YANG G.Y., 2011” (MNHN, ♀; Figs 13C, D). **Lectotype of *C. sauteri*** designated herein: “Maruyana (Form.), H. Sauter IV.1914/J. B. Corporaal: Paratype: *Callimerus bicoloripes* Pic var. *sauteri* Corp. & Pic, 1940/ *Callimerus bicoloripes sauteri* Corporaal & Pic, 1940, ZMAN type 2193.2/♂” (ZMAN, ♂; Figs 13E, F); **Paralectotype of *C. sauteri***: 5 ex., “Chosokei (Form.), H. Sauter, 1914/det. J. B. Corporaal 1939: *Callimerus prasinatus* Lewis ab. *bicoloripes* Pic/Type: *Callimerus bicoloripes* Pic var. *sauteri* Corp. & Pic, 1940 [hw. by Corporaal]/*bicoloripes* v. *sauteri* mihi [hw. by Pic]/*Callimerus bicoloripes sauteri* Corporaal & Pic, 1940, ZMAN type 2193.1/♀” (ZMAN, 1♀); “Maruyana (Form.), H. Sauter IV.1914/J. B. Corporaal: Paratype: *Callimerus bicoloripes* Pic var. *sauteri* Corp. & Pic, 1940/ *Callimerus bicoloripes sauteri* Corporaal & Pic, 1940, ZMAN type 2193.3/♀” (ZMAN, 1♀); “Kushaku, N. Formosa, Haberer/1938 ex Museum Munchen/det. J. B. Corporaal 1939: *Callimerus prasinatus* Lewis ab. *bicoloripes* Pic/J. B. Corporaal: Paratype: *Callimerus bicoloripes* Pic var. *sauteri* Corp. & Pic, 1940/ *Callimerus bicoloripes sauteri* Corporaal & Pic, 1940, ZMAN type 2193.4/♀” (ZMAN, 1♀); “J. Sonan, K. Mayake/Formosa, Shinchiku, -18.VII 1-30 [1918.VII.1-30]/det. J. B. Corporaal 1939: *Callimerus prasinatus* Lewis ab. *bicoloripes* Pic/J. B. Corporaal: Paratype: *Callimerus bicoloripes* Pic var. *sauteri* Corp. & Pic, 1940/ *Callimerus bicoloripes sauteri* Corporaal & Pic, 1940, ZMAN type 2193.5/♀” (ZMAN, 1♀); “S. Inamura, J. Sonan, M. Yoshino/Formosa, Taito, 1919.II.25-III.27/J. B. Corporaal: Paratype: *Callimerus bicoloripes* Pic var. *sauteri* Corp. & Pic, 1940/ *Callimerus bicoloripes sauteri* Corporaal & Pic, 1940, ZMAN type 2193.6/♂” (ZMAN, 1♂).

Note on type material. The lectotype of *C. sauteri* Corporaal & Pic is designated herein, as the holotype was not fixed in the original publication. This is despite the presence of holotype and paratype labels pinned to specimens, which are printed and not handwritten by the original authors. Here, I designate a male specimen as the lectotype, regardless of its paratype label.

Other material examined. China: Taiwan: Ligavon trail, Beinan Township, Taitung County, 1200 m, 2009.VII.1, CHEN Changchin leg., net (CCCC, 1♀); Ligavon trail, Beinan Township, Taitung County, 1000-1200 m, 2010.IV.17, Chou Wen-i leg. (CCCC, 3♂♂); Foshan, Sanxia Township, Taipei County, 2009.IV.23, Chou Wen-i leg. (CCCC, 1♀); Ying-tzu Ling, Pinglin Township, Taipei County, 600-950 m, 2010.V.13, CHOU Wen-i leg. (CCCC, 1♂); Chien-shan-hu, Pinglin Township, Taipei County, 500 m, 2010.V.5, CHOU Wen-i leg. (CCCC, 1♀); Shouka, Shizi Township, Pingtung County, 2000.III.17, CHOU Wen-i leg. (CCCC, 1♂); Siqu Lindao, Xinyi Township, Nantou County, 2009.VI.16, Guoboxin leg. (CCCC, 1♀); Ren'ai Township, Nantou County, 1000 m, 2008.IV.20, CHOU Wen-i leg. (CCCC, 1♀); Kuan-tao Shan, Puli Township, Nantou County, 1700 m, 1997.IV.4, CHOU Wen-i leg. (CCCC, 1♀); Kuan-tao Shan, Puli Township, Nantou County, 1400 m, 1999.V.2, CHOU Wen-i leg. (CCCC, 1♀); T'ung-men, Hualien County, 2010.IV.1, CHOU Wen-i leg. (CCCC, 2♂♂); Li-tao, Haiduan Township, Taitung City, 1000 m, 1994.IV.10, CHOU Wen-i leg. (CCCC, 1♂1♀); “Kuan-tao Shan, Nantou Hsien, Taiwan, 3-VI-1995, C. Lou leg.” (MNHN, 1♂); Taichung, Blank leg. (DEL, 1♂1♀); Region Wushe/Puli-Taiwan, Mai/Juin 1982, Coll. G. Minet (NHMB, 1♂3♀♀); Region Wushe/Puli-Taiwan, Mai/Juin 1981, Coll. G. Minet (NHMB, 1♂1♀); Paling, 700 m, Taoyuan Pref. Taiwan, 10-IV-1982, T. Shimomura leg. (MNHN, 1♀); Nr. Taman, 800 m, Taoyuan Pref. Taiwan, 23-III-1982, T. Shimomura leg. (MNHN, 1♂1♀); Nr. Suling, 1100 m, Taoyuan Pref. Taiwan, 7-IV-1982, T. Shimomura leg. (MNHN, 1♀); Nr. Paling, 700 m, Taoyuan Pref. Taiwan,

6-IV-1982, T. Shimomura leg. (MNHN, 2♂♂1♀); Formosa (MNHN, 1♀); (Near Mt. Lala) Taoyuan-Taipei H. Taiwan, May, 29th, 1978, Coll. T. Shimomura (MNHN, 1♀); (Near Meifeng) Nantou Formosa, 3. June 1976, Coll. T. Shimomura (MNHN, 1♀); (Lien hwa chi) Nantou Hsien, 750 m alt. Taiwan, 20-22 March, 1980, Coll. T. Shimomura (MNHN, 1♀); (Lien hwa chi) Nantou Hsien, 750 m alt. Taiwan, 20-22 March, 1980, Coll. T. Shimomura (MNHN, 3♂♂1♀); “Lien-hua-chih, Nantou Hsien, Taiwan, 7 Apr. 1991, Y. Okushima leg.” (MNHN, 1♀); “Sungkang, Nantou Hsien, Taiwan, 12 Apr. 1991, Y. Okushima leg.” (MNHN, 2♀♀); “Nanshanchi, Nantou Hsien, Taiwan, 10 Apr. 1991, Y. Okushima leg.” (MNHN, 1♂1♀); “Maruyama (Form.), H. Sauter IV. 1914/det J.B. Corporaal 1940: *Callimerus bicoloripes* Pic var. *sauteri* Corp. & Pic/v. *sauteri* Corp. et Pic [handwriting by Pic]/Museum Paris, Coll. M. Pic/♂” (MNHN, 1♂). **Japan:** “nr. Mt. Darumayama, Kume-jima Is., Okinawa Pref., Japan, 8-IV-1996, Y. Okushima leg.” (MNHN, 1♀); “nr. Mt. Darumayama, Kume-jima Is., Okinawa Pref., Japan, 7-IV-1996, Y. Okushima leg.” (MNHN, 3♂♂4♀♀); “nr. Mt. Darumayama, Kume-jima Is., Okinawa Pref., Japan, 5-IV-1996, Y. Okushima leg.” (MNHN, 1♀); “Mt. Āra-dake, Kume-jima Is., Okinawa Pref., Japan, 6-IV-1996, Y. Okushima leg.” (MNHN, 3♂♂1♀); “Mt. Āra-dake, Kume-jima Is., Okinawa Pref., Japan, 4-IV-1996, Y. Okushima leg.” (MNHN, 4♂♂2♀♀); “(Yona), Kunigami Son, Okinawa Pref., 5 Ap. 1990, Y. Okushima leg.” (MNHN, 2♂♂1♀); “(Mt. Yonaha-dake), Kunigami Son, Okinawa Pref., 4 Ap. 1990, Y. Okushima leg.” (MNHN, 2♂♂1♀).

FIGURE 14. Male terminalia of *Callimerus prasinatus* Lewis, 1896, one of the paralectotype in MHNH. **A–C** tegmen (**A** dorsal view **B** lateral view **C** ventral view) **D** phallus **E** spicular fork **F** tergite VIII **G** sternite VIII.

Diagnosis. *Callimerus prasinatus* shares an overlapping distribution with *C. koenigi* in Taiwan. Males of the two species are easily distinguishable: *C. prasinatus* has a triangularly emarginate tergite VIII, lacking the two hemisphere-like structures present in *C. koenigi* (a feature readily observable in dry specimens). Females of *C. prasinatus* can be differentiated from *C. koenigi* by elytral surface generally lacking scales. *C. prasinatus* differs from *C. modestus* sp. nov. by prolegs entirely yellow; male abdominal tergite VIII broadly and triangularly emarginate apically; sternite VIII with a pair of short projections apically; apices of parameres tapering, pointing

outwards, without an additional denticle (Fig. 13, 14).

Supplemental description. *Elytra*: elytral surface typically without scales; among the specimens examined, only very few possess a small number of scales near the suture. *Male legs*: yellow; meso- and metafemur-tibia joints somewhat black; dorsal surface of tarsi darkened. *Female legs*: meso- and metalegs generally darker than males; color variation present—from lightest forms (meso- and metafemur-tibia joints black) to darkest variants (meso- and metalegs completely black) (Fig. 13G–L). *Male terminalia*: tergite VIII longer than wide, with a triangular emargination apically; sternite VIII with a pair of short projections apically; apices of parameres tapering, pointing outwards; ventral surface of tegmen features an elongate heart-shaped membranous region.

Comment on synonymy. The lectotype of *C. prasinatus* designated by Kolibáč is a female, with elytra lacking scales. In the six paralectotypes, two males and three females have no scales, and one female has very few scales near elytral suture. The terminalia of the two male paralectotypes were dissected and proved to be identical (Fig. 14). Examination of additional specimens supports that *C. prasinatus* generally lacks white scales on elytra, with at most a few scales present near suture in rare specimens.

The only type series of *C. bicoloripes* we located is a female, characterized by completely black meso- and metalegs and elytra lacking scales. Among the 106 specimens examined from Taiwan and Japan, only ten share this scaleless elytral condition with the same coloration pattern, and all are females. Comparative study of both sexes revealed that, in scaleless individuals, females tend to have darker legs than males, with a continuous range of variation: from the lightest specimens, in which only the extreme apices of the meso- and metafemora and the extreme bases of the meso- and metatibiae are black, to the darkest specimens, in which the meso- and metalegs are entirely black (Fig. 13G–L). These observations demonstrate that specimens with completely black meso- and metalegs represent only a female form of *C. prasinatus*, and therefore *C. bicoloripes* is here synonymized with *C. prasinatus*.

Callimerus sauteri Corporaal & Pic, 1940 is synonymized with *C. prasinatus* based on comparisons of the male terminalia between the lectotype of the former and the paralectotypes of the latter.

Callimerus okinawanus Yajima & Nakane is synonymized with *C. prasinatus* based on comparisons of the male terminalia between topotype of the former and the paralectotypes of the latter. While the type series of *C. okinawanus* was unavailable for present study, I examined specimens from localities proximate to its original type locality: four males and two females from Mt. Yonaha, Kunigami Son, Okinawa Island; and additional 10 males and nine females from the nearby Kume-jima Island. All males were dissected, and their terminalia were confirmed to be identical to those of *C. prasinatus*. Consequently, *C. okinawanus* is synonymized with *C. prasinatus*. Most recently, Murakami (2025) independently synonymized *C. okinawanus* with *C. prasinatus*, a conclusion consistent with my own findings during the preparation of this work.

Distribution. China (Taiwan), Japan (Okinawa).

***Callimerus bicoloritarsis* Pic, 1925**

Figs 15A–B, 16, 20

bicoloritarsis Pic, 1925: 32 (*Callimerus*; type locality: “Chine”); –Corporaal & Pic 1940: 190 [*Callimerus* (*Stenocallimerus*)]; –Corporaal 1950: 83 (*Stenocallimerus*).

Type material examined. Lectotype designated here: “Chine (Guerry) / bicoloritarsis n. sp. /s. g. Stenocallimerus Corp. & Pic/ Corporaal vid. 1939 / Museum Paris, Coll. M. Pic/Type” (MNHN, ♀).

Note on type material. Lectotype is designated herein as the name-bearing type was not fixed in the original publication.

Other material examined. **China: Hubei:** China, NW Hubei 20 km, S caodian, Wudangshan, 5-7 Jul 1998, Bolm lgt, 1200m (Basel, 1♂); **Sichuan:** Sunjiagou, Shelian Village, Shelian Township, Kangding County, 1516 m, 2009.V.21, leg. Yang Ganyan, on flower, IOZ(E)1890869 (IZAS, 1♀); Detuo Township to Moxi Town, Luding County, 1300 m,

2009.V.20, leg. Yang Ganyan, on Fagaceae Flower (IZAS, 1♀); Su-Tchuen, Siào-Lou [Ya'an-Kangding road], 1897; Coll. M. Pic (MNHN, 1 ex.); Weicheng township, Yanyuan County, Liangshan Pref., 2731 m, 2014.V.3, leg. YANG Xiaodong, by sweeping net, 14Y0007 (CCCC, 1♂); same data but 14Y0008 (CCCC, 1♂); **Yunnan**: Kunming to Chuxiong, 1500–1900 m, 1956.V.18, Kryzhanovsky, IOZ(E)1124889 (IZAS, 1♂); Lancang River Valley near Baoshan, 1200 m, 1955.V.28, Kryzhanowski, IOZ(E)1124885 (IZAS, 1♂); Jinggu, 930 m, 1955.IV.23, Kryzhanowski, IOZ(E)1124888 (IZAS, 1♀); Dali suburb, 2100 m, 1955.IV.30, leg. Bushick, Zhao Yi, IOZ(E)1124884 (IZAS, 1♂); Yuanjiang Zhangba, 2006.05.05, 1878 m, Zhao Yongshuang (SWFU, 1 ex.); Kunming, 1981.V.18, Li Fasheng (CAU, 1♂); Yunnan, L.M. Comby, 1913 (MNHN, 1 ex.); “Chine, Yunnan, Recu de Lou-Nan, 1934/Callimerus pallicodipes n. sp. /var. prasinatus Lensn/Museum Paris, ex Coll. R. Oberthur” (MNHN, 1 ex.); Yunnan, H. Donckier, 1906 (MNHN, 4); Yunnan fou, H. Donckier, 1922 (MNHN, 1 ex.); “Yunnan fou/Museum Paris, Coll. Granger” (MNHN, 2); Dayao Count., Santai Town, 2140 m, 2013.V.28, leg. BI Wenxuan (CBWX, 9♂ 3♀); same data but leg. YANG Xiaodong (CCCC, 2♀); Diqing, Zhongdian, Tiger leaping Gorge, 2022 m, 2014.V.12, leg. YANG Xiaodong, by sweeping net, 14Y0107 (CCCC, 1♂); Diqing, Weixi, XiaoWeixi, 1739 m, 2014.V.20, leg. YANG Xiaodong, on flowers, 14Y0329 (CCCC, 1♂); same data but 14Y0330 (CCCC, 1♂); Yonglaga Village, Gongshan County, Nu Jiang Pref., 1560 m, 2015-VI-15, YANG Xiaodong leg., from flower, 15Y (CCCC, 1 ex.); Guogai Mountain, Erhai County, Dali City, N26°4'27", E100°8'48", 2480 m, 2021.VI.5, Song Haitian & Qi Zhihao leg. (CYGY, 5 ex.); **Guizhou**: Huaxi, 1981-V-22, Li Fasheng, 1000m (CAU, 1♀).

FIGURE 15. A, B *Callimerus bicoloritarsis* Pic, 1925, lectotype; C–E *Callimerus modestus* sp. nov., C, D holotype E a male paratype.

Diagnosis. *Callimerus bicoloritarsis* is readily distinguishable within this species group by body robust, pronotum with its length subequal to width, EL/EW 2.7–2.8, and elytra with scattered white scales not forming a pattern. Both this species and *C. koenigi* have white scales scattered over entire elytra; however, *C. bicoloritarsis* differs from the latter by body much more robust; punctures on disc of pronotum fine and sparse, with their diameters conspicuously smaller than distances between individual punctures; and male tergite VIII not swollen into two hemisphere-like structures as in *C. koenigi*.

Supplemental description. *Body:* robust. *Pronotum:* length subequal to width. *Elytra:* EL/EW 2.7–2.8; with scattering white scales without forming a pattern. *Legs:* yellow; metatarsi black; each protarsomere and mesotarsomere somewhat darker distally. *Male terminalia:* tergite VIII trapezoidal, with length equal to median width, apical margin nearly straight, in some specimens with an indistinct protrusion at middle; sternite VIII deeply emarginate apically; apices of parameres faintly hooked outwards; ventral surface of tegmen with a cordate membranous region.

Distribution. China (Hubei, Sichuan, Yunnan, Guizhou).

FIGURE 16. Male terminalia of *Callimerus bicoloritarsis* Pic, 1925, from Yunnan: A–C tegmen (A dorsal view B lateral view C ventral view A1 apex of paramere) D phallus E spicular fork F tergite VIII G sternite VIII.

***Callimerus modestus* sp. nov.**

<https://zoobank.org/98822169-06D3-464B-9889-FC241BEDA3FB>

Figs 15C–E, 17, 18B, 20

Holotype: Vietnam: “Cuc Phuong, Ninh Binh Prov., N. Vietnam, 28-IV-1996, Y. Okushima leg. / Muséum Paris, Coll. générale” (MNHN, ♂); **Paratype: Vietnam:** same as holotype (MNHN, 5♂♂5♀♀).

Diagnosis. This new species differs from *C. koenigi* by having the elytral scales restricted to the sutural region, femora of all legs with outer surface of distal three-fourths black; and male abdominal tergite VIII not swollen into two hemisphere-like structures as in *C. koenigi*. It can be distinguished from *C. prasinatus* by outer surface of distal three-fourths of profemora and outer surface of protibiae black (Fig. 15C), male abdominal tergite VIII slightly rounded apically, sternite VIII broadly emarginate apically, apices of parameres with a denticle on lateral edge (Fig. 17A).

FIGURE 17. Male terminalia of *Callimerus modestus* sp. nov., paratype as in Fig. 15E: **A–C** tegmen (**A** dorsal view **B** lateral view **C** ventral view **A1** apex of paramere) **D** phallus **E** spicular fork **F** tergite VIII **G** sternite VIII.

FIGURE 18. SEM images of elytral vestiture, solid arrow indicates lanceolate scales, hollow arrow indicates long pubescence: **A** *Callimerus angustior*, lanceolate scales form a median spot on elytra **B** *Callimerus modestus* sp. nov., lanceolate scales scatter along elytral suture without forming a distinct spot.

FIGURE 19. Distribution map of *Callimerus tenuissimus*, *C. angustior*, *C. maderi*, *C. micans*, *C. angustatus*, and *C. apicalis*.

FIGURE 20. Distribution map of *Callimerus koenigi*, *C. prasinatus*, *C. bicoloritarsis* and *C. modestus* sp. nov.

This species may be confused with *C. angustatus* and *C. apicalis* (both with a single apical spot on elytron) when elytral scales are abraded. It differs from *C. angustatus* by male abdominal sternite VIII lacking prolonged lateral lobes, and parameres with rounded apices and a lateral denticle at apex (apices of parameres narrowly triangular, denticle subapically in *C. angustatus*). It differs from *C. apicalis* by metafemoral inner surface yellow, elytral pubescence distinctly white (light golden in *C. apicalis*), male abdominal tergite VIII slightly rounded at apex (weakly emarginate medially in *C. apicalis*), dorsal sinus about twice the length of parameres (deeper in *C. apicalis*), parameres slightly convergent, and ventral membranous region slender.

Description. *Size:* length 10.4–11.2 mm, width 2.0–2.2 mm. *Color:* Head metallic dark blue, mandibles yellow with brown tip; pronotum dark blue; elytra dark blue to piceous; legs yellow, with outer surface of distal three-fourths of femora, and outer surface of tibiae black, dorsal midline of tarsi partly or entirely darkened; venter entirely dark blue. *Vesture:* body densely clothed with long, white pubescence (Fig. 15C; Fig. 18, see hollow arrow); scales scattered along elytra near suture, extending from base to apex, which may be abraded in some specimens. *Head:* EyD/EyW ca. 1.7. *Prothorax:* PL/PW ca. 1.4; pronotum proper with coarse punctures, distance between punctures in the center smaller than their diameters. *Elytra:* EL/EW ca. 3.6; with coarse punctures, distance between punctures along suture subequal to their diameters, those near the margin smaller than their diameters; apex rounded, sometimes with faintly developed outer angles. *Male terminalia:* abdominal tergite VIII rectangular, longer than wide, slightly rounded apically; sternite VIII broadly emarginate, emargination about one-third length of sternite length; parameres convergent, apices rounded, each with a denticle on lateral edge; dorsal sinus of tegmen deeper than ventral sinus, about twice the length of parameres; ventral membranous region cordiform, with straight lateral margins, and slightly longer than parameres; phallobasic apodeme one-fourth the length of tegmen; ratio of length of spicular apodeme to whole spicular fork 0.46.

Distribution. Vietnam.

Etymology. The specific epithet “modestus” is derived from the Latin adjective meaning “modest”, referring to the unornamented elytra.

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